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LEADERSHIP STYLES AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN BANKING SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Researchers and Academicians have given substantial amount of attention to investigate the link between leadership styles and organizational performance. However, the link between these two constructs remains unclear. The object of this paper therefore was to clarify the link between leadership and organizational performance by assessing the relationship between these two constructs with the focus on banking sector. This study reviewed 110 valid questionnaires sent to a randomly selected employees comprising of middle level managers of a banking company operating in the State of J&K. The study used a well established scale MLQ developed by Bass and Avolio (1997) to measure leadership styles. Organizational performance was measured using seven subjective performance measures- Sales Growth, Market Share, Profitability, Quality of Products, New Product Development, Employee Satisfaction and overall Organizational Performance. The results of this study indicate that Leadership styles have a significant impact on organizational performance. The conclusion reached that there are no one best leadership style that can fit in all situations and organizational leaders should apply the mix of both transformational and transactional leadership styles to address various issues of organizations.

Key Words: transformational leadership, transactional leadership, organizational performance, banking sector, India.

Introduction

In today's competitive business environment, organizations are under great pressures and are facing immense challenges. Under these conditions, it has become very much crucial for these organizations to differentiate themselves in the eyes of demanding customers for their sustainable survival and better performance. Several authors argued that it is the effective leadership which is the life blood for the survival of an organization and in making a perceptible difference in it (Bass, 1990; Bruke & Day, 1986; Clark & Campbell, 1992). Thus, during the past several decades the impact of leadership on performance has become an area of interest among researchers and practitioners working in the area of leadership (Cannella and Rowe, 1995; Giambatista, 2004; Rowe *et al.*, 2005). Scholars like Zhu *et al* (2005) viewed leadership as one of the key driving forces for improving firms' performance. Similarly, Dimma (1989) believes that leadership is undoubtedly the critical determinant of the success of an organization and thus determines organizational performance in the competitive global market. Bass (1990) even goes further and argued that leadership is the single most critical factor in the success or failure of an Institution.

Despite the widespread acknowledgment of the importance and value of leadership and increased research into the leadership-performance relationship, major gaps still remain unabated in our understanding. The present study is, therefore, an attempt to assess the relationship between these two constructs with the focus on Banking Sector.

Leadership-performance link: A historical overview

Like many other organizational studies, the root of leadership-performance link can be traced back to trait studies on leadership which concentrated on identifying the personality traits which characterized successful leaders (Argyris, 1955; Mohoney *et al*, 1960). These theorists further argued that successful leaders are born with some innate qualities to improve organizations performance (Stodgill, 1948). Subsequent researches however argued that it is the behaviour and style of leader that has bearing on the success of organizations (Hemphill & Coons, 1957; Likert 1961). However, scholars like Fiedler 1967; House 1971; Vroom & Yetton, 1974 shift the emphasis away from 'the one best way to lead' to 'context sensitive leadership'. However, in recent years, researchers began to refocus on 'one best way of leadership' by giving emphasis to visionary and charismatic leadership. Also recent studies on leadership have contrasted 'transactional leadership' with 'transformational leadership'.

Although the above review indicates that research into leadership has gone through periods of scepticism, yet it can be asserted that leadership acts as a defining element in the success or failure of organizations. In this context, therefore, the effective leadership is the life-blood for the survival of an organization and in making a perceptible difference in it (Bass, 1990; Burke & Day, 1986; Clark, & Campbell, 1992). As has been rightly asserted by some management analysts, the basic difference between successful and unsuccessful organization is its leadership. Schultz (1982) for example, asserts that half of all new businesses fail within first two years and only a third survive five years and in most cases poor leadership causes the failure. And, as per Katz and Kahn (1978) organizations leaders are major determinants of its success or failure. Further, the styles of leadership adapted is considered by some other researchers (e.g Awamleh,1999; Yammarino *et al* 1993) to be particularly important in achieving organizational goals and in evoking performance among subordinates (Barling *et al*, 1996; Berson *et al*, 2001; Zacharatos *et al* 2000). Similarly, today's business management attributes its successes to the leadership efficiency i.e the leadership styles of administrative supervisors which have a considerable effect on organizational performance (Terry 1960). Also, effective leadership is seen as a potent source of management development and sustained competitive advantage for organizational performance improvement (Avolio, 1999; Lado *et. al*, 1992; Rowe, 2001).

Scholars like Zhu *et al.*, (2005) viewed leadership as one of the key driving forces for improving a firm's performance. Fiedler (1996), one of the most respected researchers on leadership, even goes further to assert that the very success of a group, organization, or even an entire country depends upon the

effectiveness of a leader. Many other scholars as Sun (2002) compared the leadership styles with the leadership performance in schools and enterprises, and found that leadership styles has a significantly positive correlation with the organizational performance in both schools and enterprises. Broadly speaking, the leadership performance is identical with the organizational performance. Others also presented that executive leadership is statistically linked to firm performance (Hart & Quinn, 1993). Furthermore, empirical analysis of businesses' financial performance has found the CEO's influence 15 percent of the total variation in financial performance (Nohria, Joce, & Roberson, 2003). There are some researchers who believe that in the modern business environment; more adaptive, flexible styles of leadership are needed for modern organizations to be successful (Bass & Avolio, 1993; Bass, Avolio, Jung, & Berson, 2003). However, in the past, some researchers have argued that the actual influence of leaders on organizational outcomes is overrated and romanticized as a result of biased attributions about leaders (Meindl & Ehrlich, 1987). Similarly, House and Aditya (1997) also criticized leadership studies for focusing excessively on superior-subordinate relationships to the exclusion of several functions that leader perform, and to the exclusion of organizational and environmental variables that are crucial to mediate the leadership-performance relationship. For example, House and Aditya (1997) distinguished micro-level research and macro-level research which is supported by other researchers as well who argued that leaders and their leadership styles influence both their subordinates and organizational outcomes (Tarabishy, Solomon, Fernald and Sashkin, 2005). Recently, Fenwick and Gayle (2008), in their study of the Missing links in understanding the relationship between 'leadership and organizational performance' conclude that despite a hypothesized leadership-performance relationship suggested by some researchers, current findings are inconclusive and difficult to interpret.

From this review of related literature, it is evident that although some scholars believe that leadership enhances organizational performance while others contradict this, different concepts of leadership have been employed in different studies, making direct comparisons virtually impossible. Gaps and unanswered questions remain. The present study is, therefore, an attempt to empirically examine the relationship between these two constructs and, thus, contribute meaningfully to the body of growing literature and knowledge in this area of study.

Leadership-performance Link : empirical evidences:-

Over the past several decades, the impact of leadership styles on organizational performance has been a topic of interest among academicians and Practitioners working in the area of leadership (Cannella & Rowe, 1995; Giambatista, 2004; Rowe et al, 2005). However, empirical studies into the link between leadership and performance have been lacking.

One of the earliest detailed study examining the impact of leadership on performance has been conducted in the context of Icelandic fishing ships by Thorlindson (1987) in which the author revealed that it were the leadership skills of the captains of the ship that lead to 35- 49 percent variance in the performance of different fishing ships.

Ogbonna and Harris (2000) also carried an out a study on areas of organizational culture, leadership and organizational performance involving nearly 1000 companies in U.K. They found that the associations between leadership style studied and performance were all mediated by some form of organizational culture that was present. Leadership style was not directly linked to performance but was merely indirectly associated to it.

Xenikou and Simoso (2006) who conducted a study on 'Organizational culture and transformational leadership as predictors of business unit performance in the context of Greece found that transformational leadership was indirectly and positively linked to performance via achievement orientation. Xenikou and Simoso (2006) argued that these results show that organizational culture mediates the effect of transformational leaders on performance.

The relationship between Leadership and performance was also examined by Jaharuddin (2003) in Malaysian context by involving 74 local and 60 foreign companies in Malaysia. The results showed that leadership styles have no influence on organizational performance. In other words, leadership and organizational performance are independent of each other.

Similarly, Hancott (2005) conducted a research on the relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance in the top 100 companies in Canada. The leaders and senior managers of the top 100 companies in Canada were studied. The study had mixed results with no significant relationship found between the total CEO transformational leadership and organizational performance measured by five year stock Price change. However, there were significant relationship found between two of the individual sub-scales of transformational leadership (inspiration motivation and intellectual stimulation) and organizational performance measured by stock price changes when tenure was the control variable. CEOs tenure greater than or equal to five years play a role in organizational performance based on the findings of the study.

Rejas, Ponce, Almonte & Ponce (2006) carried out an investigation in Chile, which was aimed at finding out whether or not leadership style influences the performance of small firms. They revealed from their study that transformational leadership has a positive impact on performance, whereas transactional leadership and laissez-faire style had negative impacts

Wang, Jen, Ling (2010), also analyzed the relationship between leadership styles and organizational performance by including HRM as a third variable in the model. This study viewed 246 valid questionnaires sent to the corporate owners, executors and operators of Kaohsiung's Nanzi Export processing zone in Taiwan. To measure leadership styles they used variables as charismatic, transactional, transformational, visionary and cultural-based leadership. To measure organizational performance variables used were sales growth, net-income growth, ROI, Productivity, business performance and organizational effectiveness (degree of innovativeness, market share, and staff-turnover). It was found that charismatic, transformational and visionary of the leadership styles are positively related to organizational performance.

In the same way, one of the researches was conducted by Hernandez, (2010) on the relationship between leadership styles and performance in hospitals. Primary data for this research were collected from 109 hospital leaders via MLQ Form 5X. Results from this study indicated an increased likelihood of performance success with the application of transformational characteristics.

More recently, Obiwuru, Okwu, Akpa, Nwankwere (2011) analyzed the effects of leadership styles on organizational performance in Nigeria. The result showed that while transactional leadership style had significant positive effect on performance, transformational leadership style had positive but insignificant effect on performance. The study concluded that transactional leadership style was more appropriate in inducing performance in small scale enterprises than transformational leadership style.

Pradeep & Prabhu (2011) in their study examined the relationship between effective leadership style and employee performance in India. Their study revealed that leadership was positively linked with employee performance for both transformational behaviour and transactional contingent reward leadership behaviour.

A similar research carried out by Paracha, Qamar, Mirza, Hassan & Waqas (2012), to determine which leadership style can increase the performance of employees of some selected private schools in Pakistan, demonstrated that transactional and transformational leadership styles are both positively associated with employee performance. However, transactional leadership was found to be more significantly related to employee performance than transformational leadership style.

Muterera (2012) in his study, carried out in the United States of America, revealed that both transactional and transformational leadership behaviours are positively related with organisational

performance but that transformational leadership behaviour positively contributed to organisational performance over and above the contribution made by transactional leadership.

Based on the above contention and foregoing theoretical considerations the following four hypotheses are put forward for empirical determination:

Hypothesis1: There exists a positive correlation between Leadership styles- (transformational, transactional) and organizational performance.

Hypothesis2: Different leadership styles will have different impact on organizational performance.

Research Design and Methodology

The study sample

A sample of 200 employees comprising of middle level managers of a banking company operating in the State of J&K were selected for collecting data. Of 200 questionnaires administered to them personally, a total of 110 questionnaires were returned (55% response rate) and were usable for data analysis. The majority of respondents were male (62.7 percent) and 56.4 percent of the respondents belonged to the age group of 26-35 years. The length of service of majority of the respondents ranged from 0-5 years. Majority of respondents were educated with 65.5 percent of them as post graduates and 34.5 percent of the respondents were having bachelor's degree.

The Study instrument Used

The leadership Style was measured using Questionnaire developed by Bass & Avolio (1997) widely known as Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire Form 5X (MLQ Form 5X). The questionnaire contains 45 statements that identify and measure the key aspects of leadership behaviour, and each statement in the questionnaire relates to transactional, transformational or non-transactional leadership factors. The respondent is required to judge how frequently the behaviour described in the statement is exhibited. The MLQ uses a scale of 0 to 4, with 0 indicating a "not at all" rating of the behaviour described in the statement. The other end of the scale 4, indicates a "frequently if not always" rating of the behaviour described in the statement (Bass and Avolio, 1997).

The MLQ consists of two versions, one for the leader to complete, and one for the raters of the leaders to complete. The leaders complete a questionnaire describing their own leadership style, whilst the raters complete a questionnaire regarding the leadership style of their specific leader. The MLQ has been tested for reliability and validity in a number of settings (Pruijn and Boucher, 1994). Yammarino and Bass (1990) have proved the content and concurrent validity of the MLQ. Bass and Avolio (1997) also demonstrate the construct validity of the MLQ. The reliability of the MLQ has also been proven on many occasions through test-retest, internal consistency methods and alternative methods (Bass and Avolio, 1997). The results of these test-retest studies indicate that the components of transformational, transactional and non-transactional leadership are reliably measured by the MLQ (Bass and Avolio, 1997). The Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients calculated by Pruijn and Boucher (1994) substantiate the reliability of the MLQ. Bycio, Hackett and Allen (1995) conducted a factor analysis on the various transformational and transactional leadership variables; their findings provide further evidence of the reliability of the MLQ. The reliability of the three main leadership scales of transformational, transactional and non-transactional leadership were determined by means of Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients. Results yielded scores of 0.944, 0.736 and 0.803 respectively (Ackerman, et al., 2000).

The survey assesses the organizational performance using seven subjective measures like Sales Growth, Market Share, Profitability, Quality of Products, New Product Development, Employee Satisfaction and overall Organizational Performance. The extant literature is full of evidences using subjective measures of performance (see for example, Delaney & huselid, 1996; Denison & Mishra, 1995;

Denison et al, 2004) and inferring a moderate to strong association between subjective and objective measures of performance (see for example, Cameron, 2005; Dollinger & Golden, 1992; Guest, 2003; Pwell, 1992).

Results and Discussion

The exploration of data was undertaken by the examination of the descriptive statistics of leadership styles and organizational performance. The descriptive statistics of these variables are shown in table 1 and 2 respectively. Both the constructs used five-point scales resulting in mid-point of two. The mean score of all the leadership styles is above the midpoint of two with the exception of individualized consideration, Management by Exception, Laissez faire and non-transactional leadership as revealed in table 1. Again, measures of organizational performance are above the midpoint with reasonable dispersions of central tendency as revealed in table 2.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Leadership Styles

Dimension	Mean	Std. Deviation
Idealized Influence Attributes (IA)	2.5000	.90107
Idealized Influence Behaviours (IB)	2.2864	.77285
Inspirational Motivation (IM)	2.5636	.77699
Intellectual Stimulation (IS)	2.3795	.78235
Individualized consideration (IC)	1.9568	.76316
Contingent Reward (CR)	2.3636	.90211
Management by Exception Active (MBEA)	2.4227	.66165
Management by Exception Passive (MBEP)	1.3750	.78090
Transformational	2.3373	.69643
Transactional	2.0538	.54809

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Organizational Performance Measures.

Dimension	Mean	Std. Deviation
Sales Growth	3.6727	.70528
Market Share	3.4909	.87520
Profitability	3.545	.7619
Quality of Products or services	3.1909	.84044
New Product Development	2.9545	.85011
Employee Satisfaction	2.9818	.70362
Overall Organizational Performance	3.4364	.59858

Table 3 presents the result of the impact of transformational leadership style on organizational performance. Based on the coefficient of determination (r-square) 49.6% of the total variation in organizational performance was explained by transformational leadership style. The results of the regression also revealed a significant positive impact of transformational leadership style on organizational performance. ($\beta = 0.386$, t calculated = 13.396, t tabulated = 1.96, $p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Summary of the Regression Analysis of the effect of transformational leadership styles on organizational performance.

Regression Summary for Dependent Variable: OP R = 0.705 R ² =0.496 Adjusted R ² = 0.494 F(1,108) = 179.451, p < 0.001					
	a	Bet	Std error	T (281)	p-level
(Constant)	2	3.3	1.432	2.251	.002
Transformational Leadership	6	.38	0.029	13.396	.000

Constant=OP=organizational performance
 Independent variable= transformational leadership,

Table 4 presents the result of the impact of transactional leadership style on organizational performance. Transactional leadership style accounted for 20.5% variation in organizational performance (r square = 0.205). The results of the regression also revealed a significant positive impact of transactional leadership style on organizational performance. ($\beta = 0.582$, t calculated =6.844, t tabulated =1.96, p< 0.05).

Table 4: Summary of the Regression Analysis of the effect of transactional leadership styles on organizational performance.

Regression Summary for Dependent Variable: OP R = 0.449 R ² =0.202 Adjusted R ² = 0.194 F(1,108) = 46.841, p < 0.001					
	Beta	Std error	T (108)	p-level	
(Constant)	12.60	1.41	8.821	.000	
Transactional Leadership	.57	.087	7.136	.000	

Constant=OP=organizational performance
 Independent variable= transactional leadership,

Table 5 shows the result of Pearson correlations between each of the leadership styles and organizational performance. Result obtained showed a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and organizational performance (r = 0.0.699, p<0.05). Also, a significant positive relationship was obtained between transactional leadership style and organizational performance (r=0.430, p<0.05). Therefore, both leadership styles relates positively with organizational performance.

Table 5 Correlation between leadership and organizational performance

		Transformational leadership	Transactional leadership
Organizational Performance	Pearson Correlation	.699**	.430**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.005
	N	110	110

In hypothesis 1, transformational leadership was hypothesized to have a positive and significant effect on organizational performance, that is, that a high total score on the transformational leadership questionnaire would relate to a better organizational performance. According to the study results a significant positive relationship exists between transformational leadership style and organizational performance measures. Consequently, supervisors with transformational leadership skills would be expected to positively influence organizations performance. Transformational leadership model expands the leader’s role from simple leader–follower exchange agreements to inspiring and motivating followers to achieve goals beyond their own expectations (Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J. 2004). Transformational leaders have the ability to stimulate other leaders, colleagues, and followers to embrace new organizational perspectives, support the vision or mission of the organization, and achieve higher levels of performance

(Ardichvili, A., & Manderscheid, S. V, 2008; Avolio, B. J., & Bass, B. M, 2002; Bass, B.M., & Avolio, B.J., 1994; Bass, B. M., & Avolio, B. J.2004).

These results are in line with prior research studies. For example, Bass (1985) has suggested that transformational qualities lead to performance beyond expectations in organizational settings; research has empirically demonstrated that there is a relation between transformational attributes and organizational measure of effectiveness (Howell and Avolio, 1993; Lowe et al., 1996; Waldman et al., 2001). There are a number of other theoretical contemporary assumptions that suggest leaders who scored high on the MLQ transformational characteristics also perform better as leaders within the work environment thus promoting successful outcomes within organizations (Antonakis, Avolio, & Sivasubramaniam, 2003; Kirkbride, 2006). Contemporary researchers argue that transformational leaders coach, mentor, and empower subordinates. Such concepts increase subordinate effectiveness and heighten opportunities for organizational success. Although this research outcome is in line with the finding of previous studies see for example Rejas, Ponce, Almonte & Ponce (2006), the results of this study differs with the findings of Obiwuru, Okwu, Akpa & Nwankere (2011) who found that transformational leadership style has a positive but insignificant effect on performance. However, Obiwuru, Okwu, Akpa and Nwankere (2011) who considers transactional leadership style of having a significant positive effect on performance is in conformity with the results of this study.

Furthermore, the second hypothesis was also accepted denoting that transformational leadership style has a greater impact on organizational performance. The findings are also in consonance with the views of Pradeep & Prabhu (2011) and Muterera (2012) but do not support the views of Paracha, Qamar, Mirza, Hassan & Waqas (2012), which suggested that transactional leadership style was more significantly related than transformational leadership style to organizational performance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Effective leadership is considered as the life blood for the survival of an organization and in making a perceptible difference in it (Bass, 1990; Burke & Day, 1986; Clark, & Campbell, 1992). As has been rightly asserted by some management analysts, the basic difference between successful and unsuccessful organization is its leadership. Schultz (1982) for example, asserts that half of all new businesses fail within first two years and only a third survive five years and in most cases poor leadership causes the failure. And, as per Katz and Kahn (1978) organizations leaders are major determinants of its success or failure. Further, the styles of leadership adapted is considered by some other researchers (e.g Awamleh, 1999; Yammarino et al 1993) to be particularly important in achieving organizational goals and in evoking performance among subordinates (Barling et al, 1996; Berson et al, 2001; Zacharatos et al 2000). Similarly, today's business management attributes its successes to the leadership efficiency i.e the leadership styles of administrative supervisors which have a considerable effect on Organizational Performance (Terry 1960). Also, effective leadership is seen as a potent source of management development and sustained competitive advantage for organizational performance improvement (Avolio, 1999; Lado et. al, 1992; Rowe, 2001). Scholars like Zhu et al., (2005) viewed leadership as one of the key driving forces for improving a firm's performance. Fiedler (1996), one of the most respected researchers on leadership, even goes further to assert that the very success of a group, organization, or even an entire country depends upon the effectiveness of a leader. The most important finding of this research is that there is a significant impact of transactional and transformational leadership styles on organizational performance. The study further demonstrated that though both transformational and transactional leadership styles had a significant positive relationship with organizational performance, transformational leadership style had a strong positive relationship with organizational performance. However, there was a weak positive relationship between transactional leadership style and organizational performance. Based on these findings, the conclusion reached is that this research affirms that though transformational and transactional leadership styles are both positively related to organizational performance but transformational leadership is more significantly related and impactful on organizational performance than transactional leadership.

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations are advanced:

(i) The results that both transformational and transactional leadership styles have a significant impact on organizational performance would be useful for managers to know that there are no one best leadership style that can fit in all situations (Dastmalchian, 2000; Ogbonna and Harris 2001). Organizational leaders should apply the mix of both transformational and transactional leadership styles but with due consideration to the situation and nature of task assigned employees/followers.

(ii) Efforts should be made by the organization's top management to understand the critical factors that affect the performance of organizational members and the strategic options (training, motivation and performance appraisal) to be adopted to address them.

Furthermore, there are several limitations of study as well that affected its quality. First, the sample size is relatively small which might reduce and affect the generalizability of the findings and conclusions. Also, the results of this study are limited and constrained by the measures adopted to gauge leadership style and organizational performance. While the measures used are accepted as reliable and valid, additional insights into association may be gained by adopting different measures of leadership style and organizational performance that may reflect different perspectives.

Also, this same research can also be carried out in other countries so that a broad comparison of the concepts of leadership styles as it relate and impact on organizational performance can be made.

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